

Reliable LLM-enabled Intent-driven Management: A Validation pipeline for Network Automation

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Abstract—To democratize zero-touch network automation, we need to connect natural language user intents with formal, standards-compliant specifications. Large Language Models (LLMs) are promising but unreliable. We propose a hybrid AI-symbolic framework that uses LLMs for translation but enforces correctness with deterministic “guardrails”. Our Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) pipeline generates TM Forum-compliant intents and then validates them to ensure syntactic, semantic, and policy compliance. We benchmark our solution using three open-source LLMs, demonstrating the framework’s high reliability. It achieved a 93.8% pipeline success rate with Mistral-7B, where intents were correctly processed to a definitive conclusion. The results suggest that a hybrid architecture with symbolic guardrails offers the safety and reliability necessary for deploying generative AI in network orchestration, overcoming the limitations of using isolated LLMs.

Index Terms—TM Forum Intents, LLMs, Autonomous Networks, Intent-driven Management

I. INTRODUCTION

The shift to 5G and beyond networks enables service-oriented, automated architectures that deliver tailored services with strict QoS guarantees. This flexibility, however, brings operational complexity that traditional, manual network management cannot handle. Intent-Driven Management (IDM) has emerged as a solution, enabling operators to specify high-level goals in natural language (NL), which the network interprets and executes autonomously.

Translating user intents into precise, machine-readable specifications for network orchestration is a challenging task. Using LLMs may help, but they are unreliable when used alone in critical infrastructure, e.g, generating sometimes invalid syntax or plausible yet incorrect outputs, which in networking equates to service failure.

This paper makes three key contributions:

- **A Hybrid AI-Symbolic Architecture** with deterministic validation to safely manage LLMs.
- **A Context-Aware RAG Pipeline** that improves accuracy by splitting service and resource intent generation.
- **A Closed-Loop Validation and Correction Mechanism** that automatically detects and attempts to repair syntactically invalid LLM outputs.

We benchmarked three open-source LLMs and show that our hybrid framework not only achieves a high rate of successful automation but also effectively prevents the deployment of invalid or non-compliant services, proving its viability for real-world network orchestration.

II. RELATED WORK

The integration of LLMs into telecommunication service orchestration builds upon several converging trends: Intent-Based Networking (IBN)/Intent-driven Management (IDM), 5G/6G features, standardization efforts (e.g., ETSI, TM Forum), and the application of AI/ML in network operations.

Network service orchestration innovation takes different directions: high-level abstraction via IDM, service-oriented architecture in 5G/6G, and LLMs’ ability to generate structured data. Our work sits at the intersection, addressing the challenge of intent by translating user intents into the standardized formats as defined by the TM Forum.

A. Network Slicing Automation and Standardization

Few works deeply integrate telecommunication standards into AI-driven intent frameworks. The GSMA defined Network Slice Templates (NESTs) in JSON for standardized slice types, such as Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable Low-Latency Communication (URLLC), and Massive Machine Type Communication (mMTC) [6]. Intent is described as a set of operational goals and outcomes that a network is supposed to meet and deliver [7], specified declaratively. TM Forum defines an Intent via the intent model (TMF TR 290) [8], ontology (TMF TR 292) [9], extensions and validity (TMF TR 291) [10], and APIs (TMF 921) [11] for managing intents. Recent works explore LLMs for standards-based intent generation. In [1], an LLM-based system generates a GSMA NEST JSON from user intent and then converts it to a TMF-compliant Service Order. The system outputs a slice description wrapping the TMF Resource Ordering APIs, grounding the output in objective standards. Dandoush et al. [12] propose a conceptual multi-agent LLM system, in which LLM agents interpret user requests (e.g., “URLLC for factory IoT”) to handle multi-domain orchestration.

B. Intent-Driven Management and Zero-Touch Management

IBN and Intent-Driven Networking (IDN) [13] connect high-level service goals with network configuration for 5G and Beyond-5G (B5G) networks. In IBN, users express intents in natural language, which are automatically decomposed and enforced in the network [14]. For instance, LUMI [2] enables operators to “talk to the network” in natural language, extracting and confirming intents, and later compiles them into device configurations. Likewise, SMART [15] presents an

TABLE I
CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF LLM-BASED NETWORK AUTOMATION FRAMEWORKS

Supported Functionalities	Trantzas et al. [1]	LUMI [2]	Wei et al. [3]	Dinh et al. [4]	ARGVI [5]	Our work
Standardized intent output	✓	✗	✗	✓	✓	✓
Multi-Stage Intent Generation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
RAG for Contextual Accuracy	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓
Syntactic Validation	✗	✓	✓	✗	✓	✓
Semantic Validation	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓	✓
Policy & Resource Validation	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✓
Automated Self-Correction	✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✓

IDN concept that translates structured management intents into network configurations for autonomous operations. In [16], the authors propose a voice-enabled IBN system to manage a 5G Network. Surveys emphasize that IBN is a closed-loop process (profiling, translation, activation, assurance, etc.) and that NLP (Natural Language Processing)/ML (Machine Learning) are crucial for translating intents into actionable policies [17].

C. LLMs in Network Management and Orchestration

Recent research has explored the use of LLMs for various network management tasks. LLMs have facilitated context-aware reasoning for wireless networks, offering a new paradigm that extend beyond traditional optimization [18]–[20]. Manias et al. [21] use a customized LLM to extract intents and generate actionable network policies, reducing human intervention. Wei et al. [3] introduce IRAG (Intent-based Retrieval-Augmented Generation), which splits the source device’s configuration into fragments, extracts the intents, and uses an LLM to generate a configuration for a new device, reporting very high syntax correctness. Broadly, Trantzas et al. [1] proposed a multimodal GenAI pipeline that transforms high-level slice descriptions into machine-readable network configurations, ensuring compatibility with industry-standard APIs and orchestrators, with a focus on service ordering. These works show the potential of LLMs for orchestration. However, most employ a single-shot generation approach, directly mapping a high-level request to a final configuration, which can be fragile for complex, multi-layered tasks. In contrast, our work introduces a two-stage pipeline that decouples semantic understanding from the specification of technical resources. We also implement a context-aware RAG mechanism that delivers specialized examples for each stage, resulting in a more robust translation process. Similarly, our early work ARGVI [5] addresses model reliability by adaptively routing intents to a pool of specialized LLMs based on performance metrics.

D. Natural-Language Interfaces for Network Control

Some systems specialize in mapping natural language commands to network actions. For example, LUMI [2] enables campus network operators to issue instructions, such as “inspect traffic for the dorm,” and autonomously deploys the necessary low-level policies using ML, and operator feedback

for accurate intent interpretation and millisecond-scale compilation into commands. Similarly, in [4], the authors propose an IBN pipeline that maps user expressions to business intents and then to service intents, aligning with TM Forum’s model. The work reports improvements in LLM-based translation accuracy through the use of prompt engineering.

E. Our Contribution

While these works establish the potential of LLMs in network automation, our work introduces a more reliable framework that addresses several key gaps. Unlike approaches that rely on intermediate, domain-specific languages or employ a fragile, single-shot generation, we introduce a two-stage pipeline that decouples high-level service intent from detailed resource specification. This process is enhanced by a context-aware RAG mechanism that provides specialized examples for each generation stage, improving contextual accuracy. Furthermore, our system extends beyond simple intent classification or device configuration to generate TMF-compliant intents compatible with any standards-compliant orchestrator. Our hybrid AI-symbolic architecture integrates deterministic, non-LLM validation that checks the generated artifacts for syntactic, semantic, and policy compliance and an automated self-correction loop upon failure, ensuring a level of reliability essential for real-world deployment.

III. SYSTEM MODEL

The system architecture, shown in Fig. 1, is an end-to-end framework that translates high-level natural-language (NL) user requests into deployable network services. It generates syntactically correct and semantically accurate service and resource intents compliant with the TM Forum specifications (TR 290, 291, and 292) in Turtle(TTL) format and validates their feasibility against a simulated infrastructure.

The system has three core components: the Intent Ingestion & RAG, the Intent Generation, and the Orchestration & Routing, which directs the workflow through the pipeline. When a user submits an NL request, I_{NL} , it is first processed by the **Intent Ingestion & RAG** to retrieve relevant examples. The **Intent Generation** then performs Stage 1, generating an initial Service Intent. The **Orchestration & Routing** then parses it and verifies its correctness. For complex network slice requests, this triggers Stage 2 to produce a detailed Resource

Fig. 1. System architecture for multi-stage, RAG-based TMF Intent generation, validation, and fulfillment.

Intent. Finally, the validated Resource intent is passed to a simulated provisioning environment, completing the workflow.

A. Intent Ingestion & RAG

The Knowledge Base Manager manages a corpus of service and resource intent examples. When a new user intent, I_{NL} appears, semantic search is employed to identify and retrieve a curated set of few-shot examples, E . Our RAG approach is context-aware, selecting distinct sets of examples specific to the generation task at hand. The initial service intent generation (Stage 1) retrieves service-level examples, E_S . The subsequent resource intent generation (Stage 2) retrieves resource-level examples, E_R , ensuring that each generation stage is primed with the most relevant context.

B. Intent Generation

The system's core is the TMF Intent Generator, which uses an LLM-based generator, or "Worker", for translation tasks. It transforms any NL input, I_{NL} , into a structured TMF Service Intent, I_{S-TTL} . The Worker model M_w output is generated as:

$$O_{raw} = M_w(P_S(I_{NL}, E_S)) \quad (1)$$

Here P_S assembles the prompt from system instructions, examples E_S , and user intent I_{NL} . Post-processing then extracts the intent body I_{S-TTL} from the output O_{raw} .

The Intent Generation features multi-stage generation. For certain service types, the Service Intent I_{S-TTL} is passed to a second stage. To enhance reliability for this complex structured-to-structured task, this stage uses Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting in which the model is instructed to first explicitly reason about and list the required resource parameters before generating the final Resource Intent, I_{R-TTL} , using a distinct prompt that includes a service-specific template T_{NEST} and a new set of resource-level few-shot examples E_R :

$$I_{R-TTL} = M_w(P_R(I_{S-TTL}, T_{NEST}, E_R)). \quad (2)$$

This component has a self-correction mechanism for Service Intent I_{S-TTL} . If the syntax is invalid with an error err , a self-correction step runs, where P_C uses a correction prompt:

$$I'_{S-TTL} = M_w(P_C(I_{NL}, I_{S-TTL}, err)) \quad (3)$$

C. Orchestration & Routing

The Orchestrator manages the Orchestration & Routing, oversees the workflow, and validates the generated intents, using a rule-based Constraint Parser Validator to perform rigorous syntactic and semantic checks. This deterministic validation provides essential guardrails to safely control the probabilistic, generative nature of LLMs' outputs.

1) *Syntactic and Semantic Validation*: First, the generated I_{S-TTL} is checked for proper TTL syntax using an RDF (Resource Description Framework) parser (`rdflib`). If valid, the Orchestration & Routing uses SPARQL queries to parse critical semantic information, such as service type (from `icm:elementType`) and key service constraints. The validator parses parameters and normalizing units when needed:

- **Latency** Parses `icm:metric met:Latency` and `icm:atMost` value, in ms.
- **Bandwidth** Parses `icm:metric met:Throughput` and `icm:atLeast` value, in Mbps.
- **Budget** Parses `icm:metric met:Price` and `icm:atMost` value.
- **GPU Requirement** Parses `tech:requiresGPU` and the boolean value.
- **Client Count** Parses `icm:metric met:ConcurrentUsers` and `icm:atLeast` value.

The validation process, V , can be represented as:

$$(T_{serv}, C_{ext}, S_v) = V(I_{S-TTL}) \quad (4)$$

Here T_{serv} is the service type, C_{ext} is the set of constraints, and S_v is a boolean indicating the overall validity.

2) *Workflow Routing and Fulfillment*: The service type T_{serv} is used for routing using rule-based routing logic in the Orchestrator:

- **NEST Path**: If T_{serv} matches a predefined Network Slice as a Service type defined in the NEST (e.g., `URLLCslice`), the orchestrator will initiate Stage 2, with the generation of a detailed Resource Intent (I_{R-TTL}). The Resource Intent Parser extracts concrete resource parameters from the Resource intent, such as node UUIDs, QoS identifiers, and availability. The strict policy check is performed to validate these parameters against the NEST-compliant capabilities of the target infrastructure node.
- **Generic Path**: If T_{serv} is a generic service (e.g., `ConnectivityService`), Service To Resource Mapper translates the extracted constraints C_{ext} into abstract resource requirements. The system then searches for a suitable node in the simulated environment.

The system outputs a comprehensive result related to the Original NL request, indicating a final status of `ACCEPTED`, `REJECTED`, or `FAILED`. If rejected, a Renegotiation Suggester provides the user with interactive feedback. This closed loop validates the process from request to concrete resource allocation.

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

We benchmarked our multi-stage, RAG-based TMF Intent generation framework using tests for syntactic and semantic accuracy as well as end-to-end reliability. This section details our setup, overall LLM performance, and key scenario analysis that validate our hybrid architecture approach.

A. Experimental Setup

1) *Hardware and Software*: The experiments ran on a server with a NVIDIA RTX 6000 Ada(50GB VRAM) using Python 3.13, PyTorch, and transformers for LLM inference, and rdflib for Turtle parsing and validation.

2) *Dataset*: The benchmark utilized a dataset of 16 distinct user intents, encompassing telecommunication service types, including scenarios for standard connectivity, SD-WAN, and various GSMA-compliant Network Slice as a Service types(eMBB, mMTC, URLLC, V2X). Each entry includes a user intent(NL), and ground-truth Service and Resource Intents, a structured dictionary of ground-truth constraints, and a service category tag used by the enhanced RAG system.

3) *Models and Methodology*: We evaluated three prominent open-source LLMs of varying sizes to assess the trade-offs between model scale and task performance:

- **google/gemma-2-2b-it**(2B parameters) [22]
- **microsoft/Phi-4-mini-instruct**(3.84B parameters) [23]
- **mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3**(7B parameters) [24]

To ensure scientific validity and prevent data leakage in the RAG, we used a strict Leave-One-Out (LOO) cross-validation approach. For each of the 16 intents tested, the Knowledge Base was initialized with 15 examples, ensuring that model was not evaluated on an intent included in its few-shot context. Additionally, we enhanced the RAG mechanism with category-aware filtering to improve the contextual relevance of the selected few-shot examples.

4) *Evaluation Metrics*: We defined a hierarchy of metrics to provide a comprehensive view of system performance:

Syntactic Success Rate The percentage of intents for which the system generated a valid TMF Service Intent that could be parsed by an RDF library, including both correct initial output and those successfully repaired by self-correction.

Semantic Score (Stage 1) A composite score from 0.0 to 1.0 measuring how effectively a syntactically valid Service Intent meets the user’s requirements. It is a weighted average of three sub-metrics:

- **Identification F1-Score (60% weight)**: The F1-score for correctly identifying the set of required constraints (e.g., latency, bandwidth).
- **Value Match Accuracy (30% weight)**: The accuracy of the numeric values for well-identified constraints.
- **Unit Match Accuracy (10% weight)**: The accuracy of the units for well identified constraints.

Resource Structural Score (Stage 2) An F1-score from 0.0 to 1.0 evaluates the correctness of a generated Resource Intent by comparing the generated and ground-truth TTLs as key-value dictionaries, and penalizing missing parameters (false negatives) and extraneous or incorrect parameters (false positives).

Generation Latency (Stage 1) Time in seconds needed to generate the Service Intent, measured from LLM prompt

submission to response. This metric indicates whether the model is effective for time-sensitive operations.

Pipeline Success Rate The primary metric of system robustness: the percentage of intents processed to a clear outcome (ACCEPTED or REJECTED) without an unrecoverable error.

Task Success Rate (ACCEPTED) The percentage of intents fully translated, validated, policy-compliant, and provisioned, measures true end-to-end automation.

Guardrail Success Rate (REJECTED) The percentage of intents correctly rejected for semantic errors, policy violations, or lack of resources, quantifies the system’s safety features’ effectiveness.

System Failure Rate (FAILED) The percentage of intents not reaching a definitive conclusion, typically due to unrecoverable LLM errors, highlights critical model failures.

B. Overall Performance Analysis

Table II shows different models excelling in various stages of the complex task. It highlights the need to assess models on both component-level accuracy and overall system reliability.

TABLE II
OVERALL PERFORMANCE AND SYSTEM RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

Metric	Phi-4-mini	Gemma-2-2b	Mistral-7B
<i>Component-Level Performance</i>			
Syntax Success Rate (Stage 1)	75.0%	100%	93.8%
Avg. Semantic Score (Stage 1)	0.899	0.916	0.963
Avg. Structural Score (Stage 2)	0.764	0.708	0.822
Avg. Generation Latency (s)	20.3s	15.1s	20.5s
<i>End-to-End System Outcomes</i>			
Pipeline Success Rate	75.0%	87.5%	93.8%
Task Success Rate (ACCEPTED)	18.8%	50.0%	56.3%
Guardrail Success Rate (REJECTED)	56.2%	37.5%	31.2%
System Failure Rate (FAILED)	25.0%	12.5%	6.2%

Table II ranks clearly the models’ performance.

Mistral-7B is the top performer for end-to-end task success. It achieved the highest Task Success Rate (56.3%) and the lowest System Failure Rate (6.2%), demonstrating superior overall reliability. It achieved the highest semantic understanding (0.963 Semantic Score) and the best performance on the complex structured-to-structured resource generation task (0.822 Structural Score). Although not perfect in its initial syntax, its effective self-correction mechanism got a 93.8% Pipeline Success Rate. The end-to-end performance shows that a model needs to be able to handle the full spectrum of tasks—from NL understanding to complex code generation.

Gemma-2 excels at syntax reliability, with a 100% Syntax Success Rate, ensuring the pipeline can always proceed to the semantic validation stage. However, its scores lower in the Structural Score (0.708) and sometimes omits key ontological elements, such as `icm:elementType`, leading to a 12.5% System Failure Rate. Despite this, its strong syntax delivers a respectable 50.0% Task Success Rate, making it a highly dependable, albeit less capable, alternative.

Phi-4-mini, the smallest model, struggled most with the foundational task of generating valid syntax TTL, achieving only a 75.0% Syntax Success Rate. This bottleneck limited its ability to attempt downstream tasks, resulting in a 25.0% System Failure Rate and Task Success Rate of 18.8%. Interestingly, when it did produce valid code, its structural score (0.764) was better than Gemma-2’s, hinting at a strong potential for structured generation despite poor syntax.

We also analyzed generation latency, crucial for operational use. **Gemma-2** is the fastest, with an average latency of just 15.1 seconds. Mistral-7B and Phi-4-mini were 35% slower. This suggests that for rapid intent processing, smaller models like Gemma-2 are advantageous, though they struggle in more complex semantic tasks.

The results validate our hybrid AI-symbolic architecture. High Guardrail Success Rate (31.2 % - 56.2%) demonstrates the effectiveness of the validation logic, not system failure. These REJECTED outcomes identified subtle semantic and policy violations that would otherwise lead to misconfigurations. This proves that deterministic validation is essential for safely integrating generative AI into network orchestration.

C. Analysis of Key Scenarios

Qualitative test case analysis demonstrates the practical impact of the quantitative results and the system functionality.

1) *The Golden Path: A Complete End-to-End Success (Mistral-7B):* A URLLC slice request for a factory (“...private 5G network slice...URLLC characteristics with latency under 5ms...”)

- Stage 1 (Service Intent):** Mistral-7B accurately identified the service type as `cat:URLLCslice` and extracted all constraints (Semantic Score: 1.0).
- Routing:** The orchestrator correctly classified the service as a NEST type and provided the model with relevant, few-shot examples for URLLC for Stage 2.
- Stage 2 (Resource Intent):** With the context, the model produces a perfect resource intent (score: 1.0), correctly including `P_AccessNode`, `P_Availability ("99.999")`, and `P_SliceQoS ("82")`.
- Fulfillment:** The orchestrator verified the URLLC QoS identifier was supported and ACCEPTED the intent.

This case shows that when the model’s semantic strength and structural generation capabilities align, the system achieves full, correct, zero-touch automation.

2) *Guardrail Success: Correct Rejection due to Policy Violation (Mistral-7B):* The massive IoT (mMTC) intent (“...deploy a massive IoT network...support at least 200,000...sensors...”)

- Stage 1 & 2:** Mistral-7B correctly generated both a service and a resource intent, with score of 1.0, identifying the service as `cat:MassiveIoTConnectivity`. The LLM completed flawlessly the task as expected.
- Fulfillment:** The policy check evaluated the request against the target node resources (edge-node-paris-1). This node supports URLLC and eMBB services, but

it does *not* support Massive IoT. The system decided: "Node 'edge-node-paris-1' does not support the requested service type 'MassiveIoTConnectivity'. The request was REJECTED.

This is a successful example of the system's safety: it blocks incompatible deployments, ensuring safe automation in real-world environments.

3) *System Failure: Semantic Omission (Gemma-2)*: A custom video analytics app intent ("...deploy our custom video analytics application...") shows a subtle but critical failure that even syntactically perfect models can exhibit.

- 1) **Stage 1 (Service Intent)**: Gemma-2 produces a valid TTL output, but it missed the mandatory `icm:elementType` triple, for the service type.
- 2) **Validation**: The orchestrator confirmed the TTL syntax was valid, but found no service type.
- 3) **Fulfillment**: Without a service type, which is essential for routing the workflow, the orchestrator could not continue and was terminated and correctly marked FAILED.

This shows that perfect syntax isn't enough; the symbolic guardrails of the system must catch missing key information to prevent incomplete and ambiguous requests from advancing.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

We developed a hybrid AI-symbolic pipeline that translates natural-language requests into TMF-compliant service and resource intents. Separating LLM-based generation from validation ensures safe automated network orchestration, and our pipeline effectively handles both semantic translation and the generation of specification-compliant intents.

The larger model (Mistral-7B) achieved the best performance by balancing semantic understanding with accurate intent structure, while Gemma-2 generally produced well-formed syntax but omitted important semantic constraints. Future work will focus on improving robustness by expanding the domain dataset to mitigate data scarcity and enable a shift from in-context learning to fine-tuning smaller, specialized models for better accuracy, efficiency, and consistency. We also plan to integrate the pipeline with standards-compliant orchestrators/testbeds and extend it into a multi-turn conversational interface that helps users iteratively refine intents through dialogue.

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